

STRUCTURE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE TULIP PLANT

Khayitova Saodat Ziyadullayevna¹, Berdibekova Yulduz², Kibarov Sayfiddin²

¹English teacher at school No. 60, Sherabad district

^{1,2}Denov Entrepreneurship and Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of "Exact and Natural Sciences",
Biology, 2nd year, 1st BS-group students

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15598288>

Abstract. *This paper highlights the biological structure of the tulip, its distribution areas, role in the ecosystem, and significance in human activity. The tulip (Tulipa) belongs to the Liliaceae family and is mainly valued as an ornamental plant. The study provides information on the plant's morphological characteristics, growing conditions, achievements in selection, and its symbolic role in folklore and art.*

Keywords: *"tulip plant", "importance in nature", "role in human life", structure, morphological, ornamental plan.*

Introduction. Tulips (Tulipa) are a genus of perennial plants of the tulip family, widely distributed as ornamental plants. There are about 1,400 species worldwide, of which more than 100 are found in Eurasia and 64 in Central Asia. 25 wild species of tulips grow in Uzbekistan, but in recent years, as a result of anthropogenic factors (human activity), 24 species have been included in the International Red Book. This indicates a decrease in tulips in the natural environment.

Family: Tulipaceae

Type: Common tulip

Source: Holland

Tulips are bulbous spring plants, and their flowers are colorful, red, yellow, white, pink and other colors. About 60 varieties of tulips are grown in Uzbekistan, especially in the Botanical Garden.

External structure of a common tulip:

Picture 1. Tulip.

The importance of tulips.

1. Decorative value: Tulips are widely used as ornamental and decorative plants. Their colorful flowers, beauty and shape are used to decorate gardens, parks, orchards and other green

areas. These plants come in a variety of colors, creating an attractive landscape and attracting people.

2. Economic importance in floriculture: Tulips are of great economic importance, especially in countries such as the Netherlands. Here, tulips are grown in large volumes and exported. In Uzbekistan, tulips are also grown in gardens, which gives a special place to floriculture.

3. Role in nature conservation: Tulips are wild species, present in Uzbekistan and Central Asia, and support ecosystems and biodiversity in the natural environment. They have their own biological place in the ecosystem and create a habitat for other plants and animals.

4. International importance: Tulips are popular around the world and are used as traditional flowers by many people in different cultures and holidays, in particular, on Flower Days and others. These flowers are also often given as gifts.

5. Medical and pharmaceutical importance: Although tulips are mainly ornamental plants, some species are also used in folk medicine. Their extracts and roots have some medicinal properties, but such uses are very limited.

Protection.

1. Inclusion in the International Red Book:

Some species of tulips, especially wild species growing in Uzbekistan, are listed in the International Red Book. This means that special attention is paid to their protection and prevention of their future extinction.

In Uzbekistan, 24 wild species of tulips are listed in the International Red Book, and they are declining in the wild. To protect these species, it is necessary to preserve the ecological environment and save them from extinction.

2. Preservation of the natural environment:

It is necessary to protect the natural environment where wild tulip species grow. This, in turn, helps to preserve the habitat of various plant and animal species.

It is necessary to combat ecological and anthropogenic factors, that is, to reduce the negative impact of human activity, and to prevent the degradation of natural landscapes.

3. Support biodiversity:

Wild tulips are not limited to plants, but create interconnected systems with other biological elements of the environment, including animals and microorganisms.

4. Planting and propagation:

Propagating and transplanting wild tulips, as well as using them in landscaping, helps to preserve them.

REFERENCES

1. OzME. Volume One. Tashkent, 2000. "King 2005,". Views: 164.
2. Pollan, Michael (2002) "The Botany of Desire." United Press International
3. Archives ""World's first black tulip grown in Holland"". Views: 18 April 2019.
4. ↑ United Press International Archives „"World's first black tulip grown in Holland"".
5. „Тюльпан оритиевидный — *Tulipa orithyoides* — Описание таксона — Плантариум“. 2015-yil 14-mayda asl nusxadan [arxivlangan](#). ↑
6. *O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qizil kitobi I jild*, 2019.